

Initial best practices landscaping results

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The primary action undertaken in WP2 was to provide a comprehensive landscaping of the best practices on software quality within the research communities contributing to the EVERSE project. This objective was met by preparing and conducting a survey with the partners, in which the established practices were explored. The results of this survey will be used to fine-tune future efforts in the project and will become part of the RSQkit. It is planned that the corpus of knowledge, initiated with this first landscaping, will be expanded by additional future information collection, which will be based on the survey outcome.

Landscaping preparation

In order to identify the specific aspects of practices that should be included in the survey, a workshop was held on 31/05/2024 with 25 participants, primarily but not exclusively WP2 members, to discuss the *Dimensions of Software Quality Practices*. The initial stage of the workshop involved an exploration of the classification of software and quality practices into different types. This was followed by a discussion of the relevant aspects of quality practice types, including technical implementation, policy and management, security and ethics, and incentivisation. The aim was to identify and include all relevant aspects as widely as possible, with the workshop participants contributing to this process.

Survey implementation

On the basis of this collection, a [survey](#) was set up using the [EUSurvey platform](#). The survey comprises questions designed to evaluate current software quality practices in the research field from the perspective of the participants, as well as requests for links and examples of quality practices where available. The survey was designed to be filled by two distinct groups: firstly, EVERSE participants who were asked to contribute their expertise and insights as representatives of their respective research fields, and secondly any software expert willing to share information about their own quality practices. The survey was thus designed to allow for flexible questions depending on the selected view point and with the option to limit answers to different types of software depending on the level of use and experience of the participant with the relevant software type. Those participating in WP2 and the software pilots were requested to complete the survey and received personal invitations to do so. All EVERSE participants were invited to contribute to the survey by accessing a general link. The survey was initially open for responses from 31/07- 31/08/2024 with reminders for participation sent during this period.

Results and next steps

Close to the specified deadline, i.e. by 29/08/2024, responses to the survey had been from 11 out of 40 direct invitations, while 8 participants provided their responses via the general link. The distribution of the participants according to their experience and scientific affiliation can be seen in the figure below. It is planned to keep the survey open for some time after the milestone data to enhance participation. The compilation of guideline links will be based on the responses provided and an evaluation of software quality practices by research field. The anonymized

responses and the relevant code to access and generate statistical results from the survey will be made available in an open software repository for future use in the project and beyond.

Figure 1: Involvement of the participants in research software (left) and association to the EOSC clusters (right)